

Remote Sensing for Snowmelt-runoff Prediction in Ungauged Basins

Gary D. Moore

Johns Hopkins University, Whiting School of Engineering
gary.moore@jhu.edu

Abstract

Runoff from melting snow is a precious resource, supplying water for irrigation, livestock, and human consumption. Typically, drainage basins (basins) in developed regions are equipped with instrumentation to monitor conditions and measure flows. These data enable water managers to allocate water resources to meet demand. However, in poorly developed regions a basin may be inadequately instrumented or lack it completely. Basins lacking instrumentation are referred to as *ungauged* basins. To predict the volume of runoff from snowmelt in an *ungauged basin*, mathematical models are used to calculate runoff volume. The Snowmelt Runoff Model, initially developed in Switzerland in the 1970's, has been successfully used to model runoff in *ungauged* basins. A key input to the use of the SRM is snow cover extent. Images from remote sensing programs are uniquely suited both to identify the extent of snow cover, and to monitor changes in snow cover extent. Sensor systems used for remote sensing of snow cover are the Operational Land Imager and Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer. A general process is outlined for modeling snowmelt runoff in ungauged basins. The SRM is model is briefly discussed, and the required inputs summarized. Uncertainty error in modeling of ungauged basins are presented and discussed. Three case studies are presented; two model snowmelt runoff using the SRM on Himalayan basins; the third, for contrast, models snowmelt-runoff of an ungauged basin using only time series comparisons. The paper concludes with statements about the potential future of remote sensing and the implications for snowmelt runoff modeling.

1. Introduction

Snowmelt in drainage basins (basins) predominately located in high northern and southern latitudes is a vital source of water to many, seasonally replenishing water to streams, lakes, reservoirs, and aquifers. Basins can receive significant quantities of precipitation as snow in higher elevations; snow that melts to provide lower elevations with water. Runoff is the process of precipitation (snow) melting and subsequently moves (flows) down elevation. In rural, poorly developed areas of the World, local populations rely heavily on runoff to meet water demand for irrigation, livestock, human consumption, and to replenish aquifers. Increasingly, aquifers are over pumped to meet summer and peak demand.

An *ungauged* basin has little or no monitoring infrastructure, i.e., stream flow gauges to record snowmelt runoff volume. Water supply managers use data recorded from stream flow gauges to understand runoff variability and plan to meet water demand. Most basins located in developed regions have extensive monitoring infrastructure to measure and record the full annual precipitation-runoff cycle. Less developed areas may not have monitoring infrastructure for various reasons, e.g., weak financial resources, poor resource management, armed conflict or war). Not actively monitoring the precipitation-runoff cycle subjects populations downstream to the unpredictability of extremes highs and lows of runoff, from flooding (too much) to drought (too little).

Hydrologists who specialize in the planning and management of water resources from snowmelt have created a large number of mathematical models that is used to predict runoff from melting snow. Unfortunately, most of these models require historical stream flow volume to be known, i.e., data collected from gauging stations, making such models unsuitable to model ungauged basins. However, one model (the Snowmelt Runoff Model or SRM) originally developed in Switzerland in the 1970's and later refined by a team of researchers at the US Department of Agriculture and the Federal Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research in Switzerland *does not require* historical data to be input. Satellite remote sensing readily provides the key input i.e., the extent of snow cover, to the SRM when modeling snowmelt runoff in an ungauged basin.

Snow systems are compositionally and thermodynamically complex, and runoff in these systems can also include the contribution of melting glaciers. In this paper I do not discuss complex snow accumulation and melting dynamics, nor do I consider glacier melt contribution to runoff in ungauged basins. For sources of information on these topics please see the References section at the end of the paper.

For background, I review methods of snow identification in wide use in **Section 2 – Remote Sensing**, and discuss remote sensing systems currently in use for snow extent mapping. Knowledge of the spectral properties of snow and commonly encountered atmospheric and landscape elements allow scientists to identify and remove interfering spectral response elements from the images during spatial analysis, for example clouds, water, and rocks all of which can interfere with the process of defining snow cover extent. In **Section 3 – Modeling Process** I describe how snowmelt runoff from an ungauged basin can be predicted. I also briefly discuss the theoretical basis and required inputs to the SRM, and the importance of model calibration and validation in the modeling of an ungauged basin. In **Section 4 – Case Studies** I present an example of actual applications of the SRM in ungauged or remote regions.

2. Remote Sensing

2.1 Snow Identification

Snow can be identified in remote sensing images based on the spectral response or simply its high contrast appearance in images in the visible region (VR) of the electromagnetic spectrum (EMS). In remotely sensed images of the VR, snow can be distinguish from surrounding landcover, e.g., rocks, water, and trees, by generally being much brighter, i.e., snow's high albedo or reflectance of solar radiation. But cloud cover in remotely sensed images can conceal the earth's surface. Jensen (2007, p. 436) discusses the use of a series of images of the visible spectrum acquired at a high temporal resolution to distinguish between clouds and snow; clouds will change position in the image series, while snow accumulations over that same short time period remain stationary [1].

However, when a high temporal resolution image set of the visible spectrum is not available or there is a high percentage of cloud cover over the area of interest, snow can still be discerned using remotely sensed images from the middle infrared and microwave regions of the EMS. The radiance contrast between clouds and snow has a distinct difference from about 1.5 micrometers (μm) to 2.5 μm wavelength (Jensen, 2007, p. 436). In this wavelength range, clouds can be distinguished from snow.

Understanding the different spectral properties of snow and commonly encountered objects in the surrounding landscape, various algorithms (indexes) have been developed to simplify snow identification. An example of a widely used index that uses the different wavebands available on the Thematic Mapper (TM) sensor aboard the Landsat satellite is the Normalized Difference Snow Index (NDSI). The Landsat NDSI uses wavelength band 2 and wavelength band 5 to rapidly identify snow, and is expressed as [2]:

$$\text{Landsat TM NDSI} = \frac{(\text{TM } 2 - \text{TM } 5)}{(\text{TM } 2 + \text{TM } 5)}$$

Similarly, another snow index is used to analyze remotely sensed data from with the Moderate Resolution Spectroradiometer (MODIS) sensors, operating aboard the Terra and Aqua satellites – a two satellite system [3]. The normalized difference snow index from the MODIS sensor is expressed as:

$$\text{MODIS NDSI} = \frac{(\text{MODIS } 4 - \text{MODIS } 6)}{(\text{MODIS } 4 + \text{MODIS } 6)}$$

The Landsat and Terra/Aqua satellite missions are two of the most widely used programs for obtaining remotely sensed data on snow cover.

2.2 Highlight of Sensor Systems

Operational Land Imager (OLI) (onboard the Landsat 8 satellite)

(Historical Background: The Landsat remote sensing satellite mission is the World's longest-running remote sensing program commenced on July 23, 1972 by a group of forward thinking leaders from the US Departments of Agriculture, Interior, and the National Aeronautics and Space Commission (NASA). As of April 2016 the Landsat program has operated a total of eight satellite missions, each designed to collect earth data for a specified period of time. Since February 11, 2013 Landsat 8 (satellite mission number 8) has been (and currently is) operating at an altitude of 705 kilometers in orbit around the Earth.)

Landsat 8 operates two remote sensing sensors: the Operational Land Imager (OLI), and the Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS). Important for contemporary snow cover area mapping is the OLI providing 9 wavelength bands in the EMS from 0.43 μm to 1.39 μm . Spatial resolution is 30 meters (m) for all bands except Band 8 (panchromatic) (0.5 μm to 0.68 μm) which has a 15 m spatial resolution. Recall that the Landsat NDSI (Section 2.1) is based on Band 2 and Band 5. The OLI has a temporal resolution of 16 days and circles the Earth every 90 minutes.

A new snow cover data product, the Fractional Snow Covered Area (fSCA) product, developed by the United States Geological Survey (USGS) and derived from Landsat OLI data was announced at the 2015 meeting of the American Geophysical Union. According to the official NASA/USGS news release, the new product will accurately map fractional snow cover area in a variety of environments at a spatial scale of 30 m. Interestingly the fSCA product undergoes a unique validation process, not by using conventional ground-based sampling, but validated by using Very High Resolution Imagery. This unique approach to validation may have utility in mapping snow cover in remote *ungauged* basins where ground-based verification of snow cover extents may not be possible.

The fSCA product is not yet available for download but can be requested directly from the USGS. Web-based downloading of the fSCA data product is anticipated in 2016.

All Landsat data is available free of charge; the data can be downloaded and/or requested from the USGS. Direct downloading is possible from the following websites: USGS EarthExplorer or LandsatLook.

Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) ^{[4], [5]}

The MODIS sensor provides data for multiple scientific research programs: terrestrial, atmospheric, and oceanic; this paper is concerned only with the sensor capabilities and data products for global snow

monitoring and mapping. The Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) operates aboard the Terra and Aqua satellites at an altitude of 705 kilometers (km) with a $\pm 55^\circ$ scanning pattern provides a swath width of 2,330 km. The two satellites working together in opposite polar orbits provide worldwide temporal coverage every one to two days, collecting data in 36 spectral bands from 0.4 μm to 14.4 μm . The spatial resolution of images and data depend on which data products are used, and vary from 500 m to 0.05° by 0.05° . MODIS' snow detection algorithm is based on the use of near infrared data collected at 1.6 μm (MODIS band 6).

A wide range of snow cover mapping products are produced by NASA using raw data gathered by the MODIS sensor. Special algorithms have been developed to identify and isolate snow cover from landscape and atmospheric interferences. For example, Level 3 data products daily and composite images of eight day cycles at 500 m spatial resolution. Also included in a Level 3 product are data on sea ice extent and temperature at 1 km spatial resolution – but this paper is concerned only with snow cover products.

Landcover type influences the accuracy of MODIS snow mapping. General error estimates are derived from initial field measurements of different landcover types and, based on this, error is expected to be highest (~10%) in boreal forests in November to April. Snowdata products consist of seven sub-products, each step in the sub-product preparation contain unique spatial and spectral characteristics which must be understood by the user. The characteristics inherent in the step-wise sub-products should be considered as limitations that transfer into the final snow cover product, thus should be analyzed, considered carefully, and documented by the product user.

Other Remote Sensors

There are many other remote sensing programs, from the commercial sector (with data products available for purchase), government sponsored programs with products available at no or low cost. Here is an example list of programs that have a potential to collected snow extent data:

- AVHRR (Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer, NOAA (USA))
- GOES (Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite National Environmental Satellite, Data, and Information Service (NESDIS) (USA)(North and South America only)
- SPOT (*Satellite Pour l'Observation de la Terre*) commercial program (France);
- IKONOS (Greek meaning image), commercial (USA)
- Quickbird commercial program (no longer in orbit but several years historical data are available), US Corporation [*DigitalGlobe*] based in Colorado) (USA)
- ASTER (Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer), cooperative USA and Japan program (USA-Japan)
- MERIS (Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer), European Space Agency (replaced by the Sentinel satellite now in orbit) (EU)
- ERS-1 and ERS-2, (European Remote Sensing Satellite), European Space Agency (both satellites no longer in service) (EU)
- RADARSAT (Radar Satellite), Canadian Space Agency, (current out of service, but with plans to launch a constellation of satellites in 2018) (Canada)

2.3 A Modeling Process

A general approach to predictive modeling of snowmelt in ungauged basins consists of the following steps:

1. Clearly define the objectives of predictive modeling

2. Select an appropriate mathematical model
3. Define the drainage basin extents (use a topographic map and/or digital elevation model)
4. Identify the major surface water features receiving snowmelt runoff
5. Compile sources for other key model inputs, for example, atmospheric temperature and precipitation (model dependent)
6. Perform predictive modeling
7. If possible, validate predictive modeling results by comparing predicted runoff volume with actual surface water flow. Positive agreement between the predicted runoff volume and the actual flow volume builds confidence in the model predictive capability and the modeling process.

Numerous mathematical models using different theoretical approaches, e.g., conventional physical system model or thermodynamic system model have been developed to predict runoff volume from snowmelt. Most of these models require input of actual surface water flow volumes to run the model; this type of model is not suitable for predictive modeling of ungauged basins. However, one model that has found wide acceptance on a global scale for the predictive modeling of ungauged basins is the Snowmelt Runoff Model (SRM). The SRM is briefly described below.

The SRM was originally developed by Jaroslav Martinec in 1975 and later enhanced in collaboration with a group of researchers from US Department of Agriculture [6][7]. According to SRM's published documentation, the SRM can be used to "simulate daily flows in a snowmelt season, in a year, or in a sequence of years. The results can be compared with the measured runoff (*if available*) in order to assess the performance of the model and to verify the values of the model parameters. Simulations can also serve to evaluate runoff patterns in ungauged basins using satellite monitoring of snow covered areas and extrapolation of temperatures and precipitation from nearby stations" (*comment added*).

The SRM is a mathematical model defined in the following equation (Martinec, J. et al., 2004, 2008):

$$Q_{n+1} = \sum_{i=1}^N [c_{Sn,i} \cdot a_{n,i} (T_n + \Delta T_n) S_{n,i} + c_{Rn,i} P_{n,i}] A \frac{10,000}{86,400} (1 - k_{n+1}) + Q_n k_{n+1}$$

where: Q = average daily discharge [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$]
c = runoff coefficient expressing the losses as a ratio (runoff/precipitation), [c_s snow and c_R for rain]
a = degree day factor [$\text{cm } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$] indicating the snowmelt depth resulting from 1 degree-day
T = number of degree-days [$^\circ\text{C d}$]
 ΔT = the adjustment by temperature lapse rate when extrapolating the temperature from the station to the average hypsometric elevation of the basin or zone [$^\circ\text{C d}$]
S = ratio of the snow covered area to the total area
P = precipitation contributing to runoff [cm]. A preselected threshold temperature, T_{crit} , determines whether this contribution is rainfall and immediate. If precipitation is determined by T_{crit} to the new snow, it is kept on storage over the hitherto snow free area until melting conditions occur.
A = area of the basin or zone [km^2]
k = recession coefficient, decline of discharge during non-runoff
n = sequence of days. The equation is written for a time lag of 18 hours between the temperature cycle and the discharge cycle, various time lags can be introduced
N = number of elevation zones into which the basin is divided
 $\frac{10,000}{86,400}$ = conversion from [$\text{cm km}^2 \text{d}^{-1}$] to [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$]

SRM was originally developed for use on relatively small basins in Europe. However, since the model's introduction in 1975, advancements in the remote sensing of snow cover have permitted larger and larger basins to be modeled [8]. As of 2000, SRM has been used to model 80 basins in 25 countries, with the largest basin to be modeled 122,000 km² [9]. Rango (1992) reviewed 50 case studies where SRM was used to model snowmelt-runoff dynamics [10]. Based on that review, he concluded SRM could be applied to different climatic regions.

2.4 Snowmelt Runoff Model Inputs

Unlike other mathematical snowmelt-runoff models that require a large number of inputs and historical flow data to optimize the runoff model, the SRM does not require extensive parameterization nor historical flow data.

Required SRM Inputs:

1. Basin area (derived from topographic map or digital elevation model)
2. Temperature (if onsite data are unavailable, derived from regional/global weather database and/or forecasting models)
3. Precipitation (if onsite data are unavailable, derived from regional/global weather database and/or forecasting models)
4. Snow covered area (from remote sensing)
5. Runoff coefficient (snow + rain) (measured or estimated by a professional hydrological judgment)

2.5 Uncertainty Error in Modeling Snowmelt Runoff

Uncertainty produces errors in snowmelt runoff modeling in a number of ways, for example:

- Poor conceptualization of the physical basin
Inaccurately defining the boundaries of a basin will introduce error into the runoff volume calculation. For example, if a basin's estimated extent is undersized relative to its true size, the resulting calculated volume of runoff will be less than the actual volume.
- Changing global climate
Uncertainty is also introduced when the effects of a changing climate are encountered. This kind of error could be encountered when, for example, a database of historical temperature measurements is statistically extrapolated and projected over the uninstrumented basin to be modeled. However, because of climate change, those historical data may no longer be representative of future temperatures.
- Unauthorized surface water diversions (prior to the gauge measurement, if any)
Unauthorized surface water diversions (upstream of the river flow gauging station or measuring point), a very common occurrence in developing regions that lack the institutional capacity to manage water resource allocation, can result in the measured flow being less than the model predicted flow.

3. Modeling Case Studies

Three case studies are presented in this section. Each was carefully selected to illustrate the estimation of snowmelt runoff in ungauged basins. Two of the case studies are located in basins of the Himalayas; the third is located in the Andes. Both of the basin studies in the Himalayas use the SRM model and

remote sensing derived snow cover as input to the model. The basin study in the Andes is unique and is presented as contrast and comparison to the Himalayan basin studies. The Andes study does not use the SRM because of extreme data paucity, i.e., no temperature data are available for the study area. Instead the investigators use fundamental science of the empirically-derived time series graphs to understand the snowmelt-runoff relationship.

3.1 Test of Snowmelt-Runoff Model for a Major River Basin in Western Himalayas (Dey, B., et al., 1989) in *Nordic Hydrology*^[11]

The authors describe the use of the Snowmelt Runoff Model (SRM) to predict seasonal snowmelt-derived surface water runoff for a basin located in the western Himalayas. A number of snowmelt runoff models was available (1989) for predicting surface water runoff from snowmelt but most were judged to be too complex in terms of the input data required to make a simulation viable. Complexity in this context was situational - the basin to be studied is located in a remote, western Himalayas of South Asia, poorly ungauged and unmonitored basin yet vital resource supplying to meet the water demand from a growing population for irrigation, water supply, and aquifer recharge. The authors present a summary of snowmelt dynamics to explain the fundamental basis of the SRM – that it is a relatively simple process-response model based on degree-days; atmospheric temperature is directly related to the amount of snowmelt runoff.

The authors compare the SRM to other models requiring extensive inputs in an effort to better describe the snowmelt-runoff process. For example, an energy balance model of a snowmelt-runoff system may require inputs such as data on thermal signals and the changing albedo of snow, solar radiation, percent cloud cover, and convection heat transfer – measurements not routinely or easily made, thus making this type of model of little if any practical use. The author described the SRM as being used to model a broad variety of basin of varying size, and over periods of a few days to an entire year. Another key input to the SRM is snow cover extent, which satellite remote sensing data is able to easily acquire. Two other basic inputs that are routinely monitored and relatively easy to acquire or statistically calculate based on global network of monitor stations are temperature and precipitation. The SRM uses these inputs to calculate an estimate of runoff discharge. Importantly SRM can be used to make predictions of runoff discharge without reference to historical records of stream flow, thus giving it utility for use in ungauged or poorly gauged basins.

The case study is for the drainage basin of the Kabul River which drains an area of 63,657 square kilometers (km²) (24,578 square miles). The basin generally consist of folded and faulted geology of the Alpine-Karakoram system of the Hindukush Mountains. The elevation of the basin varies from 305 meters (m) (1,000 feet (ft)) to 7,690 m (25,230 ft). Glaciers occupy 1 percent of the total area of the Kabul basin and thus glacier melt is considered to contribute a negligible amount to river discharge. The sole gauging station on the Kabul River identified in this case study is located in Nowshera at an elevation of 305 m (1,000 ft). Basin runoff in the Himalayas is characterized by high seasonal runoff volumes from snowmelt in some areas accounting for 70 percent of total basin runoff as river flow. Thus snowmelt is a major resource that needs to be understood if water resources are to be managed effectively to meet demand.

Daily snow cover in the basin was estimated from National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) -4 satellite imagery. (*Note: the NOAA-4 satellite was equipped with VHRR (Very High Resolution Radiometer), VTPR (Vertical Temperature Profile Radiometer), and SR (Scanning Radiometer) sensors. The satellite was operational on November 15, 1974 and decommissioned as scheduled on November 18, 1978 [12].*) The authors calculated an estimated average elevation of the basin, and the change in temperature with elevation was also estimated. SRM model performance for

daily calculations was examined using the Nash-Sutcliffe R^2 value. The R^2 test compares observed and computed runoff volume.

The results indicated poor agreement between observed and calculated runoff volumes for the initial simulation on the basin. Inaccessibility and sparse data for the large, remote basin were the reasons the authors suggested for the poor agreement. The authors adjusted the input values for temperature / elevation change rate, and the mean elevation for the basin where the majority of snowmelt occurs, and ran the SRM model a second time. The second simulation exhibited much improved agreement between predicted and observed runoff volume ($R^2 = 0.66$; the R^2 is a *more is better* measure and the highest value obtainable is 1.0). Although this R^2 value is an improvement over the initial simulation, the authors suggested that temperature inputs, which were not from the basin (no weather station) and had been inferred the nearest weather station located in Mardan, Pakistan, 360 km (223 miles) to the east. Mardan has a hot, dry continental climate, very different from the Himalayan basins. The R^2 value from the second simulation is consistent with prior modeling work in Himalayan basins.

The authors conclude by suggesting that the accuracy of future simulations may be improved with the use of more representative data for the basin, including the increased snow cover products from satellite-based remote sensing missions; this is especially important for data sparse, remote regions. This study showed that the SRM is valid for use on remote basin with sparse data. Lastly, based on the author's experience, large gains in predictive accuracy can be achieved by use of quality, site-specific data for climate and snow cover.

3.2 Modeling Snowmelt-runoff under climate scenarios in the Hunza River Basin, Karakorma Range, Northern Pakistan (Tahir, A.A., et al., 2011) in *Journal of Hydrology*^[13]

In this case study, the authors describe the use of the Snowmelt Runoff Model (SRM) for basin contributions to the Indus River, with headwaters located in the Karakoram Range of the western Himalayan mountains. This agricultural-based economy in Pakistan is dependent on water supply for irrigation from the Indus River. Thus prediction of runoff volumes and timing from snow and glacier melt for water supply planning and management to meet growing demand for this critical water resource is needed. As the Indus River leaves the mountains, it flows into the Tarbela reservoir. The land area that contributes runoff from snow and glacier melt to the Indus River is called the Upper Indus Basin (UIB).

The authors provide a review of climate change literature to describe some of the predictions for how the climate of this area may change. Climate change studies of the Greater Himalayan region indicate increasing temperatures, forecast to increase summer runoff from snow and glacier melting from 16 to 50 percent. However, the forecast for the study area (Western Himalayas), dominated by snow accumulation not monsoonal rains as in the greater Himalayan region, is an increase in temperature of up to 4.8 °C (8.64 °F) and precipitation by up to 16 percent by 2100.

The authors apply the SRM model on the Hunza River Basin (13,733 km²), a major snow and glacier melt fed tributary to the Indus River. Previous use of the SRM to basins in the Himalayas can be used to predict the snow and glacier melt runoff in the Hunza Basin on a daily time scale, as well as investigate the effects of future climate scenarios on runoff. The authors indicate the SRM is less sensitive to precipitation inputs, and more sensitive to snow cover and temperature inputs. The following dataset were used to prepare inputs to the SRM model. Topography: The Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER), Global Digital Elevation Model (GDEM) was used to delineate the basin boundaries. (*Note: The authors did not indicate the vertical resolution of the GDEM. According to published information from NASA and the METI of Japan the GDEM has a vertical resolution of 20 m at 95 percent confidence.*) Hydrometeorological data: stream flow measured by development authority of Pakistan. Precipitation data: statistically inferred from a database of

measurements from monitoring stations over the region. Snow cover data: MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer).

The specific MODIS product used was the 8-day L3 Global 500 m Grid (MOD10A2). This dataset contains a data field for the maximum snow cover extent over an eight day period. The basin extent was overlaid on the MODIS dataset, enabling the MODIS data to be subsampled for the area of the basin only. Where cloud cover exceeded 20 percent on any given day, the data record for that day was deleted, and the average snow cover of the day preceding and the day after was used. Multiple climate scenarios were modeled using the SRM model to assess the effects on runoff within the basin.

The authors conclude that increasing temperatures will increase the volume of stream flow within the region. The results will be useful to water resource planners for considering future demand, storage, and supply scenarios for irrigation and potable supply.

3.3 Remote Sensing of Andean Mountain Snow cover to Forecast water discharge of Cuyo Rivers (Delbart, N., et al., 2015) in *Revue de geographic alpine* ^[14]

The SRM model or other model was not used in this case study. The reason for this, according to the authors was that while stream flow data were available for the basin, precipitation and temperature data were not – temperature being a key *required* input to the SRM model. The authors conducted time series analyses of flow data from four watersheds and snow cover extent mapping of the same watershed to derive empirical rules for the discharge-snowmelt relationship. This study builds on prior work conducted by these authors assessing the correlation between river discharge and snow cover in the Andean Mountains. In this next phase, the authors refine their original results to investigate using optical remote sensing products of snow cover extent to forecast water shortages.

First, to define the areas contributing runoff to four rivers flow into an unnamed dam, the authors used a digital elevation model (DEM) derived from the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission. The (vertical) spatial resolution of the DEM was not provided. The resulting four watersheds were: Mendoza (area = 7,108 km²), Tunuyan (area = 2,460 km²), the Diamante (area = 2,762 km²) and the Atuel (3,035 km²). Snow cover extents were mapped and monitored using the snow cover data products obtained from the MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer). The MODIS MOD10A2 product was processed with the Normalized Difference Snow Index (NDSI); an NDSI value of close to 1 mean snow covers most of the pixel being analyzed, and an NDSI value close to -1 means the pixel under analysis is not snow covered. Each MOD10A2 8-day image is a composite of all the measured snow cover data for the eight-day period. Pixels with clouds were removed from the analysis, and snow bed less than is less than 1 centimeter in thickness (corresponding to a 0.07 NDSI). The error inherent in the MODIS product selected is neither presented nor addressed in the case study. Also, it is unclear if the MODIS product selected had already been processed using the NDSI; if this is the case, the investigators used the NDSI (for a second time) to transform data to identify snow cover. The effects on the snow product and/or the study results, if any, from *repeated* use of the NDSI are not discussed.

The authors found good correlation between snow cover extents and the discharge rates in each of the four watersheds; the area of best data agreement was during peak flow periods. Poor data correlation was observed for other periods, with the worst during periods of low flow. The results still represented an improvement over prior methods of forecasting, and therefore this simple approach may be useful to water resource managers for planning of storage and delivery to meet increasing water demand for irrigation and potable supply. The authors cite one way to improve predictive results of future studies is to use the snowmelt-runoff model (SRM) – but they point out that key inputs such as temperature and precipitation are not available in this remote area of the Andes.

4. Conclusion

4.1 The Future of Remote Sensing: Implications for Snow Mapping

Our capabilities to more precisely map and monitor snow cover by remote sensing will improve in the coming decades. Khorram et al. (2016) recognizes several trends in the remote sensing industry which are summarized below [15]:

- Growth of public-private partnerships for satellite construction and operation, bring innovation and reducing cost of satellite systems.
- Innovation smaller, more efficient systems routinely delivering sub-meter (a few 10's of centimeters) spatial resolutions, enhanced multispectral and hyperspectral resolutions (more efficient cooling systems so more of the electromagnetic spectrum can be accessed), both light detection and ranging (LiDAR) and differential absorption (DIAL) LiDAR systems from geostationary orbit for precision landscape measurement.
- Tunable (custom selection of wavelengths) imaging systems to become commonplace.
- Many orbiting systems to provide real-time data access (consumer access to the data direct from the orbiting platform)
- Integration of big data (land, hydro, and climate) with remote sensing systems

There predictions of the development of remote sensing technology and systems mean better systems to map and monitor snow cover. And more integration with land-based data on climate, surface water, and aquifer systems has the potential to advance our capabilities to build useful models of ungauged basins, and to improve predictions of surface water flows from snowmelt for more accurate forecasts for water supply and flood management.

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